

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, March- 2023 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10106644

THE USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS IN SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

The pandemic we are experiencing has only accelerated the growth of technology in education. Teachers have been forced to develop skills with the most diverse digital tools in order to continue the teaching and learning process. Knowing the importance and compulsory nature of Physical Education in Brazilian basic education, this subject was, like all the others, adapted, where through ICT (information and communication technology) it was possible to promote and experience interactive, dynamic and practical classes as well. Every day was a new challenge to face, but this experience brought teachers learning and techno-scientific mastery. Even after returning to face-to-face classes, the technological tools became allies in the teaching-learning process, attracting students' attention and becoming another option to help physical education teachers in their practical and theoretical experience.